

Impact of Social Media Influencer Interactivity and Authenticity on Impulsive Buying Behaviour: Mediating Role of Attitude and Brand Attachment

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Abstract

This study aimed to know the impact of social media influencer interactivity and authenticity on impulsive buying behaviour of consumers of Pakistan. For mediating the relation between them attitude toward the influencer and brand attachment was used. This study talks about the social media influencer interactivity and authenticity using as the perception in affecting the attitude toward the influencer and brand attachment which increases the impulsive buying behaviour. Influencer marketing was the new trend and understanding the relation between clothing brands and social media influencer was necessary. The attitude toward the influencer and brand attachment help as a mediator to mediate the relation between them. Research was conducted using the survey-based questionnaire and collected responses from consumers of clothing brands in Pakistan. The data was collected from a total of 332 respondents, which was used in data analysis. The tools used to test the research were SPSS and AMOS. The study's conclusions stated that social media influencer interactivity does not has a significant and beneficial influence on impulsive buying. The relation show that social media influencer interactivity and authenticity put their impact on attitude toward the influencer and brand attachment. The influence of attitude toward the influencer on impulsive buying behaviour was non-significant, contrary to other research' results indicating that brand attachment was necessary to increase the impulsive buying behaviour of young consumers. The study's implications stated that it was conducted to know the impact of social media influencer interactivity and authenticity impacting the impulsive buying behaviour of consumers of Pakistan. Attitude toward the influencer and brand attachment help in increasing the relation between them.

Keywords: Social media influencer interactivity, social media influencer authenticity, attitude toward the influencer, brand attachment, impulsive buying behaviour

1. Introduction

Many aspects of our lives have been transformed by the digital revolution. People now have a virtual presence instead of a physical one, from consuming news and social media updates through smartphones to buying for groceries online to hailing a taxi. Any interruption in alerts, reminders, or advertisements was considered as a nuisance in a society where consumers demand everything to be at their fingertips (Kowalczyk & Pounders, 2016). Over-the-top services like Netflix and Amazon Prime continue to erode print and television's market share, and the media environment was changing dramatically. Even as marketers use social media, websites, blogs, and offline channels like television, print, and radio, the challenge was to get the advertising content and brand message understood by an ever-distracted consumer. Consumers have been shown in recent studies to have low recall of ads and even worse, to have forgotten the brand message (Lou & Yuan, 2019). Ad blockers and similar technologies were used by consumers to avoid online advertisements. In today's world, when consumers have short attention spans and a plethora of electronic devices compete for their attention, marketers have an uphill struggle to be heard over the din. Marketers were increasingly using brand stories to engage customers because they know that stories with an emotional hook have a far higher chance of being shared (Chopra et al., 2021).

Many companies have an Instagram account, but social media influencers, people with large followings on various platforms, were becoming more important to marketing efforts because they help buyers feel more connected to a business. Brands were increasingly using "ordinary people" who have a large following on social media to engage with their customers and potential customers (Wu & Stilwell, 2017).

In contrast, over 4.70 billion social media influencers exist worldwide (Howell, 2017). With the growing popularity of social media influencers in Pakistan and little academic research undertaken in the Pakistani context, the authors decided to study the social media influencer marketing landscape, especially from the point of view of young consumers of this developing country. As a medium allowing limitless access to a tremendous amount of information worldwide, social media has become part of its users' daily routine (Chopra et al., 2021). The expanding numbers of social media users impacted marketing trends and tactics, and marketers started considering social media platforms as vital avenues to connect and interact with clients (Bianchi et al., 2017). A few years ago, firms used celebrities'

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popularity and social standing to advertise their brands. However, improvements in social media platforms led to an upward recognition of social media influencers (Xu & Pratt, 2018). Sometimes referred to as opinion leaders, social media influencers constantly share their daily life activities, abilities, views, and suggestions based on experience or knowledge (Freberg et al., 2011). The enormous rise in the number of social media influencers' followers prompted the emergence of social media influencer marketing as a fast-rising marketing strategy in several sectors. Fashion was one of the areas in which social media influencer marketing has been highly studied in recent years. With the continually rising demands in the fashion sector, buyers were getting more fashion-sensitive, and purchasing habits were significantly impacted by fashion trends (Quelhas-Brito et al., 2020). Such trends were most typically led by social media influencers or leaders (Ki & Kim, 2019). Social media influencers were people with a significant number of followers on social media who provide fashion content and have the capacity to sway followers' opinions and buying behaviour. They were seen as new participants in the fashion business since they attract consumers with a high interest in attractive fashion clothing (Britt et al., 2020). Thus far, there is a paucity of research discussing the links between social media influencer interactivity and authenticity and consumer impulse buying (Park & Armstrong, 2019). This study intends to address this gap in the literature by evaluating factors determining attitudes toward the social media influencer and brand attachment. De Veirman et al. (2017) propose that a crucial problem for marketers was discovering social media influencers that would better complement their advertising strategy; such social media influencers should exhibit excellent persuasion skills to attract followers.

The primary purpose of this research was to identify the existence of such a preference, as well as to investigate the factors that contribute to its formation and the pace at which it spreads. In addition, the topic of impulsive purchase, a particular kind of shopping behaviour that was prevalent among young customers, was studied in this research as it relates to the retail industry. According to Khan et al. (2015), impulsive buying accounts for thirty to fifty percent of all purchasing, and around ninety percent of buyers make purchases on the spur of the moment. Pakistan was included on the list of hidden heroes among ten markets that were anticipated to register remarkable growth in the retail sector in the coming years. Ten emerging economies with massive potential for an increase in the retail sector were identified; among these economies, Pakistan was one of the markets. According to Qamar et al. (2020), the wholesale and retail sectors were worth Rs 3.6 trillion in Pakistan, which was almost 18 percent of GDP. The wholesale and retail sectors have the highest share in the service sector at 31.1 percent, and they also registered the highest growth at 6.82 percent in the past years.

1.1. Objectives

The objectives of the current study were:

- To understand the importance of influencer marketing.
- To get the knowledge about impulsive buying behaviour in young consumers.
- To know about the impact of brand attachment and attitude toward the influencer on impulsive buying.
- To check the social media interactivity and social media authenticity increasing impulsive buying of young consumers.
- To understand the relationship between social media influencer interactivity and attitude toward the influencer.
- To understand the relationship between social media influencer authenticity and brand attachment.

1.2. Significance of the Study

The significance of the current study was to provide a way for the marketers to target the social media influencers for their clothing brands to increase their sales of the products. The increasing trend of influencer marketing can improvise young consumers to buy things to match the influencer's image impulsively. The present study signifies the role of social media influencer interactivity and authenticity in the increasing impulsive buying of young consumers. The attitude toward the influencer and brand attachment can either make this impact positive or negative depending upon the influencer's activities.

2. Literature Review

Influencer marketing identifies and employs opinion leaders who can influence potential consumers and participate in a brand's marketing efforts through sponsored content (Lou & Yuan, 2019). Opinion leaders' importance as influential information providers were emphasized. The relevance of opinion leaders has risen due to the recent explosion of social media since many consumers seek peer advice while making purchasing decisions. While social media has long been used to manage customer relationships Weismueller et al. (2020), it was now increasingly used to identify opinion leaders and reach out to consumers. For example, fitness, cuisine, or video games were some of the topics that influencers cover on social media platforms such as YouTube, Twitter, Instagram, and Facebook. Social media influencers may be followed and communicated with by those interested in a given issue to keep abreast of the most

recent news and trends. To put it simply, a social media influencer was a person who regularly posts useful information to their social media accounts in order to build an audience that was beneficial to a company (Lou and Yuan, 2019). The terms "social media social media influencer" and "social media influencer endorsement" were used here. Social media influencer marketing's impact has been studied in various scenarios (De Veirman et al., 2017). The majority of studies emphasized social media influencers' distinctiveness e.g., credibility, amount of followers and discovered that this uniqueness was the underlying cause for their efficacy. Social media influencers, such as 'You tubers' and 'Instafamous' personalities, were more influential than traditional celebrities, according to (Kusumasondjaja, 2019). Furthermore, the perceived trustworthiness of You tubers i.e., video bloggers can improve brand attitudes (Reinikainen et al., 2020). Instagram social media influencers with many followers were also shown to be more likable and popular (De Veirman et al., 2017).

2.1. Social Media Influencer Interactivity

Social media influencer interactivity was a two-way dialogue between the user and the social media influencer. It might be in the form of comments or criticism left by users on social media influencers' profiles. Users of prior media found it difficult to communicate directly with their celebrities (Lee & Kim, 2020). However, with the growth of the internet, both the social media influencer and the user may communicate effectively. The internet has given followers the ability to like or hate their favorite social media influencer's posts and images. It has also allowed other users to view people's messages to the social media influencer. Internet interactivity was not new in research, and it was commonly used for websites to see brand engagement on websites (Furedi, 2010).

2.2. Social Media Influencer Interactivity and Attitude toward the Influencer

Interactivity is a technical feature integrated within a communication channel that permits or restricts specific behaviours (Burgoon et al., 2000). However, since customers may pick what to read on studies have revealed that increasing interactivity or adding more hyperlinks could lead to selective skimming of news material, a poor predictor of learning (Eveland & Dunwoody, 2002). Users spent the least amount of time on a shopping website with the greatest degree of multimodal engagement, according to Xu and Sundar (2016), which affected their recall and recognition memory of product information. Modality interaction grabs consumers' attention by giving a dynamic user experience Trivedi and Sama (2020), yet the enhanced user involvement comes at a cost. According to Liu et al. (2019), clothing brands may not do enough to converse with customers on social media to fulfill or surpass their expectations. Conversational interactivity's most essential feature was that it improves two-way communication between brands and consumers and establishes a reciprocal relationship (Yu & Hu, 2020). According to the research on clothing brand online communities, interaction improves the perception of interactivity and, as a result, the attitude toward the social media influencer toward these clothing brands Kim and Lee (2019), implying that high interactivity has a beneficial impact on social media advertising.

H1: social media influencer interactivity has a significant impact on attitude toward the social media influencer.

2.3. Social Media Influencer Interactivity and Brand Attachment

Interactivity between social media influencers and their followers may lead to attitudes toward the social media influencer to the clothing brand. Interpersonal involvement has been compared to relatedness in prior research. Relatedness was described as a person's need to feel near to others, and it was directly linked to brand connection to clothing brands (Aw & Labrecque, 2020). In order to develop an attitude toward the social media influencer with social media influencer businesses, it was also vital to improve closeness and engagement. Although social media influencers and followers may not know each other, vigorous two-way dialogue on social media makes customers feel connected to social media influencers.

When customers view a brand as having human-like features, an attitude toward the influencer can grow stronger, similar to how individuals might have a strong attitude toward the clothing brand (Kowalczyk & Pounders, 2016). As a human brand, social media influencer brands allow for the most active real-time contact between the business and its followers. As a result, customers may form an attitude toward social media influencers. People's perceptions of impulsive buying in social media marketing improve as they become more active online (Tatar & Eren-Erdogmus, 2016). If a business provides practical solutions to customers on its microblogs and actively engages with them, confidence in that clothing brand increases (Coyle et al., 2012).

H2: social media influencer interactivity has a significant impact on brand attachment.

2.4. Social Media Influencer Authenticity

Social media influencer authenticity was a concept that describes a social media influencer's commitment to sharing and generating content by relying on intrinsic and self-motivation. The notion of social media influencer authenticity was derived from social media influencer authenticity, in which the brand manager was self-motivated and enthusiastic about selling items to consumers (Audrezet et al., 2020). Social media influencer brands were now using the same method. They depict themselves as brand managers and enthusiastically share their material, causing followers to

become more engaged with the topic. Audrezet et al. (2020) proposes the term "passionate authenticity," which implies that the process of generating content was a self-gratifying activity for the social media influencer. According to earlier studies Dwivedi and McDonald (2018), social media influencer authenticity was a subjective term that plays with the customers' minds. It focuses on the consumers' perceptions and interpretations of the brands in their minds. The notion of social media influencer authenticity helps create a brand image in the eyes of customers. According to Schallehn et al. (2014), it aids the brand in developing the link between the consumer and the brand. To achieve a difference in the view of consumers, social media influencer authenticity was required.

2.5. Social Media Influencer Authenticity and Brand Attachment

Vintage brands like the Volkswagen Beetle and Star Wars have a "spirit of the past," which Arya and colleagues (2019) described as a brand's "aura" or essence that was linked to the brand's specific sense of historical legacy. To begin, buyers' perceptions of the legitimacy of social media influencers might be skewed by their own social constructions (Vrontis et al., 2020). A customer's interpretation and perception of observed brand behaviour was what social media influencers allude to when they talk about object authenticity (Beverland et al., 2010). An genuine social media influencer refers to how consumers perceive the brand's enthusiasm, commitment, and openness about its internal aims, all of which were reflected in the brand's management (Moulard et al., 2016). Rather than external or financial reasons, authentic social media influencers generate material based on internal motivations e.g., inherently rewarding and delightful. Authenticity is considered a significant ingredient in building emotional attachments in the flow of extant research on human brands (Marwick & Boyd, 2011). When shared preferences of categorically similar persons in an audience were represented in such perceptions of authenticity, the appeal of authentic producers' offers was likely to be greater than that of other producers (Bruhn et al., 2012). According to research, there were unspoken linkages between customer perceptions of social media influencer authenticity and brand marketing communications. For example, respondents in Bruhn et al. (2012)'s study gave positive ratings to brand marketing communications for brands judged to be accurate, indicating a possible explanatory link.

H3: social media influencer authenticity has a significant impact on brand attachment.

2.6. Social Media Influencer Authenticity and Attitude toward the Influencer

Social media influencer authenticity judgments were impacted by the point of view of the individuals making the judgment Sidali and Hemmerling (2014), their knowledge and expectations, and their ambitions. "Social media influencer authenticity was ultimately not about facts per se, but rather about judgement around those facts," argues (Kovács, 2019). Not just for marketing but also for management theories that locate company identity in its audiences Koçak et al. (2014) or for genuine leadership theories that frequently make implicit assumptions about what "followers" of leaders perceive authentic. Morhart et al. (2015) established a scale to assess consumers' perceptions of social media influencer authenticity and discovered that they identified the impact of brand attachment increasing the impulsive buying behaviour of consumers toward the clothing line in Pakistan.

Although Audrezet et al. (2020)'s work offers significant background for this study, it was also vital to give a critical viewpoint on branding constructs as found by other researchers. Rather than being an objective representation with evidence-based criteria, influencer authenticity was formed subjectively via social and personal evaluations (Steiner & Reisinger, 2006). In other words, even in the absence of objective criteria for a cultural experience, purchasers were more likely to construct their feeling of authenticity. Brand attachment relates to a company's manufacturing practices and the building of an overall genuine brand message (Alexander, 2009).

H4: social media influencer authenticity has a significant impact on attitude toward the influencer.

2.7. Social Media Influencer Interactivity and Impulsive Buying Behaviour

There were several ways to describe interactivity, from the communication process itself to the media or technology used to implement it (Quiring, 2009). Media/technology-based interaction was distinct from user-experienced interactivity. An interface's actual interactivity was more of a predictor of outcome variables than was its perceived interactivity (Zhao & Lu, 2012). A website's trustworthiness may be increased if it responds quickly to users' requests for information and gives them a sense of control over its operations. More happy customers and positive sentiments of the website were also common (Zhao & Lu, 2012).

Interactivity Through online interactions, social media allows advertisers and marketers to develop close relationships with their customers Kelly et al. (2010) and create value for luxury brands. Interactivity can be viewed from three angles. The current study takes a situational approach, emphasizing dialogue and linking social media conversation responsiveness to the concept of interactivity (Ainin et al., 2015). Previous research in this field has focused on the assumptions of the "environmental theory of retail revolution," which underlines substantial consequences for retailing's survival owing to environmental change (Yiu & Xu, 2012). The environmental theory's novel assumption originates from Darwin's "natural selection theory," which analyzes "survival of the fittest" and predicts that only those species that can adapt to environmental changes would survive. However, Zhang et al. (2018) claims that the online clothes brand atmosphere affects customers' emotions, which leads to increased impulse buying.

H5: social media influencer interactivity significant impact on impulsive buying behaviour.

2.8. Social Media Influencer Authenticity and Impulsive Buying Behaviour

According to reports, an influencer who supplies product information adores consumers and answers their questions boost the impulsive buying process (Yu & Bastin, 2017). Professional personnel also help customers avoid frustration by assisting as they shop. According to specific research, the effect of brand attachment and attitude in clothing brands should be considered a significant aspect (Saad & Metawie, 2015).

The notion of social media influencer authenticity has been used in business literature in various ways to convey different connotations. On the other hand, social media influencer authenticity was more usually referred to as an influencer's actuality, sincerity, genuineness, originality, or truthfulness (Chen et al., 2019). Previous consumer behaviour and marketing studies have agreed on the relevance of influencer authenticity in expressing meaning to customers and its relationship to brand attachment and impulsive buying behaviour (Maraz et al., 2016).

Recently, Zhang et al. (2021) investigated the concept of social media influencer authenticity from the standpoint of brands of clothes, producing impulsive buying behaviour. Importantly, Vukadin et al. (2019), among others, argue that several of the constructions' conceptual bounds were hazy. In a study conducted by Shahjehan, Qureshi, Zeb, and Saifullah (2012), it was discovered that impulsive buying was strongly linked to neuroticism, indicating that consumers who experience emotional instability, anxiety, moodiness, irritability, or sadness were more likely to engage in impulsive purchasing.

H6: social media influencer authenticity has significant influence on impulsive buying behaviour.

2.9. Attitude toward the Influencer

It was crucial to understand the consumers' attitudes around social media influencers in order to determine social media influencer authenticity and engagement. According to the source attractiveness model, a social media influencer's production of a favorable attitude can lead to a consumer's buy intention (Chan 2013). Thanks to content sharing, the social media influencer may offer items or services to his followers instead of brand managers (Lim 2017). Consumers' attitudes regarding social media influencers reveal that positive and negative assessments can impact their behaviour. According to (Ajzen 2011), the stronger the consumer's attitude toward the social media influencer, the stronger the consumer's conduct toward the social media influencer. According to previous research, there was a clear correlation between influencer attitudes and influencer interactivity. Consumers use clothing brands to convey their identity to others, according to Reed et al. (2012), and they judge others based on their impulse purchase behaviour. Consumers were more likely to follow social media influencers that have comparable personality features, a similar lifestyle, or similar tastes, Pratt (2018). Positive views toward social media influencers were reflected in higher levels of congruence between social media influencers and potential consumers, which leads to impulsive buying behaviour.

H7: attitude toward the influencer has a significant influence on impulsive buying behaviour.

2.10. Brand Attachment

The phrase "brand attachment" comes from (Bowlby 1979)'s attachment theory, which states that a link between a customer and a brand was based on emotions. This relationship was defined as a bond formed between a kid and a caregiver due to their affection. The belief that creates the relationship between the consumer and the brand was brand attachment (Khan and Fatima 2017). The brand attachment creates a strong relationship between the customer and the brand because of the emotional connection. This also gives the impression to the customer that the brand has met their expectations. According to Wu (2017), marketing scholars employ attachment theory to determine relationships between individuals, brands, and businesses. According to previous research (Japutra 2017), customers who form emotional bonds with companies were more committed to them. According to (Hwang 2019), brand attachment was more critical in determining customer buying behaviour toward a brand than brand attitude.

Marketing researchers define brand attachment as the strength of the link that connects a brand to the self, and its relevance in driving brand equity has been recognized (Park et al., 2010; Zhou et al., 2012). The self-brand connection and brand prominence were the two dimensions that make up the brand image. According to previous research, consumers who were emotionally linked to a brand or business were more likely to be loyal to it (Hwang et al., 2019).

H8: brand attachment has a significant influence on impulsive buying behaviour.

2.11. Attitude toward the Influencer as a Mediator

When customers feel in charge of an activity, Al-Debei et al. (2013) find that they were more inclined to engage in it. Perceptions of behavioural control, according to the TPB, have a positive impact on both attitudes and intentions. Perceptions of behavioural control, attitudes toward behaviour, and subjective norms all have a role in intention, according to the TPB (Ajzen, 2011). Impulsive shopping was influenced by family, according to Baker, Moschis, Rigdon, and Fatt (2016). The length of time spent shopping has been linked to impulsive purchases, according to several studies. Consumers' need for time-saving and convenience-enhancing products was explained by the economic theory in marketing literature. When a consumer remains in the shop for a longer period of time, the more probable it was that they would purchase anything on impulse (Foroughi et al., 2012; Underhill, 2009). In a study of consumer

behaviour and personality, Bratko, Butkovic, and Bosnjak (2013) revealed that phenol-type relationships with impulsivity and extraversion were mostly prompted by overlapping genetic manipulators. Then, the hypothesis were: H9: attitude toward the influencer mediates the relation between social media influencer interactivity and impulsive buying behaviour.

H10: attitude toward the influencer mediates the relation between social media influencer authenticity and impulsive buying behaviour of consumers.

2.12. Brand Attachment as a Mediator

Consumers believe in their own self-worth and behave accordingly. Using this example, we can see how people discover and create emotional ties to companies that complement their self-concept (Lou & Yuan). There were a variety of reasons why people engage in word-of-mouth marketing, and marketers may exploit these psychological motivations to induce pro-brand behaviour (Lovett et al, 2013). By encouraging customers to develop positive self-perceptions that lead to brand loyalty, it was our hope that this strategy will enhance the amount of social media engagement. Clothing brands' social media pages gain in popularity when a client "likes" them, which has been shown to increase sales (Lee et al., 2015).

According to attachment theory, consumers were obliged to commit their resources, such as time and effort, to maintain closeness to others, in this instance, the brand. An emotional connection to a brand increases a customer's likelihood of public support and advocacy (Zhou et al., 2012). Previously, researchers discovered that brand attachment mediates the link between actual and ideal self-congruency and compulsive buying (Japutra et al., 2017, 2018). Customers' impulsive purchase behaviour was linked to brand attachment, which may act as a mediating factor. As a result of their desire to acquire more value from their purchase, consumers who view social media influencers to be honest were more likely to participate in impulsive purchasing (Kandampully et al., 2015).

Thus, the above discussion led to the hypotheses:

H11: brand attachment mediates the relation between social media influencer authenticity and impulsive buying behaviour of consumers.

H12: Brand attachment mediates the relation between social media influencer interactivity and impulsive buying behaviour.

3. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

The above conceptual framework of the current study shows that influencer marketing was the most recent trend in attracting more customers to the clothing brands in Pakistan. Due to the increase in social media usage among young consumers, they were getting attracted to content creators. Many marketers of clothing brands use influencer marketing to get the attention of young consumers towards their brands. In the current study, social media influencer interactivity and authenticity were used as the independent variables to check their impact on increasing the impulsive buying behaviour of consumers. So the content shared by them has more authenticity and interactivity and can engage the young consumers of Pakistan on a personal level. That can urge these young consumers to buy impulsively from clothing brands.

Impulsive buying behaviour was used as the dependent variable because among young consumers of Pakistan, and it was becoming more popular to get products from clothing brands without any need. They see the influencer using the products in his/her content and want to buy them, which increases the impulsive buying behaviour of consumers. The

current study uses attitude toward the influencer and brand attachment as mediators. The increasing trend of influencer marketing attitude of young consumers also triggers their impulsive buying behaviour toward the clothing brands. The second mediator in the current study was brand attachment. Brand attachment was the term used by many clothing brands in Pakistan to attract consumers to their products. Brand attachment increases the young consumers' narrative about their favorite clothing brands. That can be the reason to have more impulsive buying of their products. The current study's novelty was to use influencer marketing as the gap because it was the emerging trend in marketing products and services.

4. Methodology

The current research was based on the positivism. In this researcher collects data, analyze it and then postulate the results and conclusion on it. The research method used in the current study was the quantitative method. The primary research method used in the present study was the questionnaire. For secondary purposes, different journals, websites, and books were consulted to get the literature about the variables. The deductive approach was used in the study to test the impact of social media influencer interactivity and authenticity on the impulsive buying behaviour of consumers. An explanatory study was conducted on a topic that has never been investigated before. In the current study, the research strategy used was the survey. The survey was chosen because social media has become a powerful platform, and the people of Pakistan were also getting involved in it more and more.

The data collection tools used in the study were both primary and secondary. The secondary tool contains the different journals and papers published by the authorized authors stating these variables and their impact on their study. The books were consulted to know about the different theories used to define the relation of these variables to each other. The primary data collection used for the present study is the questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed based on a five-point Likert scale. The variable social media influencer interactivity contains five items proposed by McMillan and Hwang (2002) and (Thorson and Rodgers 2006). There were three items for social media influencer authenticity, and they were adapted from the (Moulard et al. 2016). The dependent variable of the study was impulsive buying behaviour. That contains five items that were proposed by (Ridgway et al. 2008). The present study has two mediators: attitude toward the influencer and brand attachment. The items for the attitude toward the influencer were adapted from Azjen (2011) and Casalo (2018) and contain four items. The brand attachment contains six items, and they were proposed by Dwivedi (2014), Stokburger Sauer (2012), and (Han 2010).

The sample size of the current study was 332 participants. The sampling technique defined for the current study was simple random sampling. For data analysis, the tools used in the current research were the SPSS and AMOS. SPSS was used to check the validity and normality of the data.

The ethical consideration of the present study was that the respondent's personal information was not shared with anyone. It was just used for research purposes.

5. Data Analysis and Results

5.1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The first question of the questionnaire was the gender of the respondents. It contains two options: one was male, and the other was female. The male respondents of the current study are 182, and the female respondents are 150. So, the total number of respondents was 332. Then, the percentage was calculated for the male and females. It said that males were at 54.8 percent and females were at 45.2 percent. So, that means the social media was used more by the young male consumers who built more interest in fulfilling the study's questionnaire.

Table 1: Demographic profile (Gender)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	male	182	54.8	54.8	54.8
	female	150	45.2	45.2	100.0
	Total	332	100.0	100.0	

The next was the age of the consumers. The less than 18-year respondent was 108, 18 to 22 years are 131, 23 to 26 years are 78, and more than 26 are 15. So, according to our research, the data was corrected to target only young consumers. To avoid distortion, the researcher eliminates the respondent who was more than this age category responses. The percentage calculated for the age are 32.5, 39.5, 23.5, and 4.5, respectively.

The next was the studying of the young consumers. The public sector students were 199, and the private sector students were 133. There percentage calculated states that they were 59.9 and 40.1, respectively.

Table 1: Demographic profile (Age)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less Than 18 Year	108	32.5	32.5	32.5
	18 to 22 Years	131	39.5	39.5	72.0
	23 to 26 Years	78	23.5	23.5	95.5
	More Than 26 Years	15	4.5	4.5	100.0
	Total	332	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Demographic profile (Study)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Public	199	59.9	59.9	59.9
	Private	133	40.1	40.1	100.0
	Total	332	100.0	100.0	

Education was the next demographic of the questionnaire. It contains four options: college/inter, bachelors, masters, and Ph.D. the responses from these options were: 49, 141, 132, and 10. So, the percentage calculated for them was 14.8% for college, 42.5% for bachelor's, 39.8% for master's, and 3.0% for Ph.D. this means that the respondents are more from the bachelor's program.

Table 4: Demographic profile (Education)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	College/ Inter	49	14.8	14.8	14.8
	Bachelors	141	42.5	42.5	57.2
	Masters	132	39.8	39.8	97.0
	Ph.D.	10	3.0	3.0	100.0
	Total	332	100.0	100.0	

The next is the family income of the respondents. Young consumers of the current study stated their family income was among the options: 10000-20000, 21000-35000, 36000-50000, and 51000-65000. The respondents select the options 46, 148, 107, and 31. The percentage calculated for these options was 13.9%, 44.6%, 32.2%, and 9.3%.

Table 3: Demographic profile (Income)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	10000-20000	46	13.9	13.9	13.9
	21000-35000	148	44.6	44.6	58.4
	36000-50000	107	32.2	32.2	90.7
	51000-65000	31	9.3	9.3	100.0
	Total	332	100.0	100.0	

5.2. Reliability Analysis

Social media influencer interactivity, and social media influencer authenticity have alpha values of 0.919 and 0.899, respectively, whereas attitude toward the influencer has an alpha value of 0.892 and was very reliable. Brand attachment, as measured by 0.944, was also acceptable. For impulsive buying behaviour, Cronbach's alpha was 0.918.

5.3. Descriptive Analysis

The minimum value of social media interactivity was 1.00, and the maximum was 5.00. Then the mean statistic value was 3.2114, and the standard deviation has the value of 1.00066. The skewness statistic stands at -.272, and the standard error was .134. The second variable was the social media influencer authenticity. The minimum value of social media influencer interactivity was 1.00, and the maximum was 5.00. Then the mean statistic value was 3.3303, and the standard deviation has the value of 1.01101. The skewness statistic stands at -.352, and the standard error was .134.

The following variable was the attitude toward the influencer. The minimum value of attitude toward the influencer was 1.00, and the maximum was 5.00. Then the mean statistic value was 3.4450, and the standard deviation has the value of 1.11963. The skewness statistic stands at -.472, and the standard error was .134. The following variable was brand attachment. The minimum value of brand attachment was 1.00, and the maximum was 5.00. Then the mean

statistic value was 3.4317, and the standard deviation has the value of 1.12541. The skewness statistic stands at -.512, and the standard error was .134. The next was impulsive buying behaviour. The minimum value of impulsive buying behaviour was 1.00, and the maximum was 5.00. Then the mean statistic value was 3.5096, and the standard deviation has the value of 1.08904. The skewness statistic stands at -.483, and the standard error was .134.

Table 6: Reliability Analysis

Sr #	Variables	No. of items	Cronbach's Alpha
1	INI	5	0.919
2	INA	3	0.899
3	ATI	4	0.892
4	BA	6	0.944
5	IBB	5	0.918

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Std. Error
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
InfluInter	332	1.00	5.00	3.2114	1.00066	-.272	.134
InfluAuth	332	1.00	5.00	3.3303	1.01101	-.352	.134
AttituInflu	332	1.00	5.00	3.4450	1.11963	-.472	.134
BrandAttach	332	1.00	5.00	3.4317	1.12541	-.512	.134
ImpBuyBeh	332	1.00	5.00	3.5096	1.08904	-.483	.134
Valid N listwise	332						

5.4. Convergent and Discriminant Validity

The variables BA, INI, INA, ATI, and IBB have the composite reliability value of 0.944, 0.919, 0.900, 0.891, and 0.919. That means all the values were greater than 0.7. The threshold value of AVE is 0.50. The variables have the value of 0.739, 0.693, 0.750, 0.672, and 0.693. The next test was the MSV which state that all variables have the values 0.319, 0.326, 0.326, 0.319, 0.301.

The BA has the highest value of 0.859 in the fourth column of the table. The INI has a high value of 0.832 in the fifth column of the table. The INA has a high value of 0.866 in the sixth column of the table among the other variables. ATI has the highest value, 0.820 in the seventh column of the table, and IBB has a 0.833 value in the eighth column of the table.

Table 8: Convergent and Discriminant Validity

	CR	AVE	MSV	BA	INI	INA	ATI	IBB
BA	0.944	0.739	0.319	0.859				
INI	0.919	0.693	0.326	0.506	0.832			
INA	0.900	0.750	0.326	0.478	0.571	0.866		
ATI	0.891	0.672	0.319	0.565	0.517	0.500	0.820	
IBB	0.919	0.693	0.301	0.479	0.492	0.549	0.421	0.833

5.5. Confirmatory Factor Analysis

The CMIN means the threshold range should be less or equal to 3. In the table below, the value of CMIN was 2.307, which means it was valid. The GFI and the threshold range should be equal to or greater than 0.80. In the table, the value was 0.877, which was in alignment. The CFI has a threshold range equal to or greater than 0.90. The current value in the table was 0.953, which was valid for the data. IFI, which has a threshold value equal to or greater than 0.90. The current value in the table was 0.953. That was in alignment with the data. RMSEA has a threshold range of less or equal to 0.08, and in the table, it was 0.063, which was less than 0.08.

Table 9: Model Fit Indices

Indicators	Threshold range	Current values
CMIN/DF	Less or equal 3	2.307
GFI	Equal or greater .80	.877
CFI	Equal or greater .90	.953
IFI	Equal or greater .90	.953
RMSEA	Less or equal .08	.063

5.6. Measurement Model

The numbers stated in the model seem to be all more than 0.3. As a result, it was legitimate and standard to use as a measuring model. The measurement model also has the best fit model, for which data was evaluated, and scale modeling was tested. CMIN/DF 2.307, GFI 0.877, CFI 0.953, IFI 0.953, and RMSEA 0.063 were the values in the table.

Figure 2: Measurement model

5.7. Structural Equation Modeling

The study's first hypothesis was an essential link between social media influencer interactivity and attitude toward the influencer. The result shows three ***, indicating that H1 was acceptable. Brand attachment impact on social media influencer interactivity and social media influencer authenticity have the same three ***, indicating that their hypotheses were also accepted, and that brand attachment has a considerable influence on social media influencer interactivity and social media influencer authenticity, which was the study's H2 and H3 hypothesis.

In the table above, social media influencer authenticity and attitude toward the influencer also have *** three stars, indicating that hypothesis H4 was accepted. However, the social media influencer interactivity and impulsive buying behaviour H5 hypothesis was rejected, indicating have a value of 0.002. The social media influencer authenticity and impulsive buying behaviour H6 hypothesis shows that it has *** three stars, indicating a meaningful relationship between them. However, the H7 hypothesis has a value in the table of 0.290. That means there was no significant relationship between attitude toward the influencer and impulsive buying behaviour, and the hypothesis was rejected. Another clear link exists between brand attachment and impulsive buying behaviour. The chart reveals a route relationship that has *** three stars. That was to say, the H8 hypothesis was accepted.

5.8. Standardized Indirect Effects

So, according to the study's hypothesis H9, attitude toward the influencer influences the relationship between social media influencer interactivity and impulsive buying behaviour. The value was .069** in the table indicates that the hypothesis was accepted. Similarly, the H10 hypothesis claims that brand attachment influences the relationship between social media influencer authenticity and impulsive buying behaviour. The hypothesis was accepted, and brand attachment mediates the impact on social media influencer authenticity and impulsive buying behaviour. The value in the above table .087**, indicating a partial mediation impact of the variable on the social media influencer authenticity and impulsive buying behaviour.

Table 10: Structural Equation Modeling

	Path		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
AttituInflu	<---	InfluInter	.325	.061	5.922	***
BrandAttach	<---	InfluInter	.341	.061	6.260	***
BrandAttach	<---	InfluAuth	.265	.061	4.860	***
AttituInflu	<---	InfluAuth	.272	.061	4.966	***
ImpBuyBeh	<---	InfluInter	.176	.063	3.054	.002
ImpBuyBeh	<---	InfluAuth	.303	.060	5.429	***
ImpBuyBeh	<---	AttituInflu	.055	.051	1.059	.290
ImpBuyBeh	<---	BrandAttach	.202	.051	3.837	***

Table 11: Indirect Effects

	InfluAuth	InfluInter	BrandAttach	AttituInflu
BrandAttach	.000	.000	.000	.000
AttituInflu	.000	.000	.000	.000
ImpBuyBeh	.069**	.087**	.000	.000

6. Discussion

Consumers' information sources and interactions with brands and businesses have altered dramatically due to social media. Consumers use social media to get information and develop relationships with companies (Hair et al., 2010; Booth & Matic, 2011). As a result, businesses were devoting more of their marketing money to social media influencers than conventional marketing channels (Phua et al., 2017). Influencer marketing was a popular method for increasing consumer brand awareness and purchase behaviour by using the power of influential people (Ahmad, 2018). The relevance of this study was underscored by the rise in the number of social media influencers who act as human brands online. This study adds to our understanding of how consumers perceive influencers on social media and the impact of impulsive buying behaviour in buying products from clothing brands. Both social media influencer interactivity and authenticity should consider an attitude toward the influencer and brand attachment. Attitude toward the influencer predicted favorable views toward the influencer and purchase intentions in the complete model. This result was in line with earlier research on attitude (Amos et al., 2008). In addition, social media influencer interactivity predicted impulsive buying behaviour in the route model. The positive and robust link between the two variables further supports this. Even though social media influencer authenticity predicts positive brand attachment in the whole model since likeability captured most of this impact, attractiveness does predict impulsive buying behaviour considerably.

This research backs up the idea that social media influencer interactivity was a strong predictor of purchase intent, emphasizing the significance of this trait. According to the results of the whole model, social media influencer interactivity seems to be a significant component of attitude toward the influencer. This was in line with past research on attitude toward the influencer (Reinhard et al., 2006). Although attitude toward the influencer did not significantly influence impulsive buying behaviour in the entire regression model, there was a small but significant association between attitude toward the influencer and impulsive buying behaviour. Social media influencer interactivity still predicts attitude toward the influencer. In the present study, attitude toward the influencer work as a mediator to increase the proximity between the social media influencer interactivity and impulsive buying behaviour. The dissemination of knowledge may cause brands to become aware of the social media influencer, resulting in mutually beneficial commercial relationships. If brand management wants to market their product or service via an influencer, social media influencer authenticity was a crucial trait for the influencer to have. Social media influencer authenticity was more likely to acquire followers in the future, making them more appealing to brand managers looking to reach a broader and more targeted audience. The urge to get more followers, on the other hand, may lead influencers to purchase followers or even fabricate brand partnerships, which might damage their reputation if detected (Cole, 2019). In the complete model analysis, brand attachment seems essential for social media influencer authenticity and can increase. Although the data confirm earlier evidence showing similarity leads to good assessments (Choi & Rifon, 2012), as observed with positive brand attachment, attitude toward the influencer does not impact on getting the impulsive buying behaviour. The importance of intimacy in the connections between followers and influencers has gone unexplored. According to the data, brand attachment seems to be a crucial mediator when an influencer lacks one of the other favorable attributes (attractiveness, likeability, and similarity). Brand attachment, in other words, may operate as a buffer when an influencer lacks a particular attribute.

Brand attachment mitigated the impact of impulsive buying behaviour. Even if an influencer was ugly, buy intentions were still high if the followers identify as close to the influencer. This discovery has significant consequences for brand managers and influencers. Business partnerships with attractive influencers should not be the primary focus of brand management. This was because those who identify as interpersonally connected to influencers were equally as influential in influencing impulsive buying for the product or service. The attitude toward the influencer mediates the relation between the social media influencer's interactivity and impulsive buying behaviour. That can create havoc in increasing the interest of consumers of Pakistan towards the clothing brands. They buy more products from them just because their favorite influencer wears them.

7. Conclusion

This research looked at the effect of the closeness of social media influencer interactivity, social media influencer authenticity, attitude toward the influencer, and brand attachment. Social media influencer engagement plays a crucial role in the influencer's attitude and purchase intents, according to this study, and should be carefully analyzed by brand managers and social media influencers. Research exploring the effect of social media influencer interaction and authenticity on other known predictors, which include attitude toward the influencer and brand attachment, to improve the impact of impulsive purchase behaviour. Social media Influencers are better at managing themselves as personal brands, while brand managers were better at finding prominent social media influencers. Consumer-brand interactions were altering owing to the rise of social media engagement and authenticity and the persuasive personalities of social media influencers. Using the source credibility model, various marketing studies explored the impact of celebrities and influencers on attitudes, word-of-mouth, and purchase intentions. However, other academics have urged for new models and techniques to assessing source characteristics (Lemanski and Hyung-Seok, 2012).

7.1. Managerial implications

From a managerial standpoint, this study shows that customers with low brand attachment have low impulsive buying behaviour than those with high brand attachment, resulting in more impulsive purchases from the customers. Consumers' interaction due to brand attachment and social media interactivity can work on emotions, which can help create a profitable strategy.

7.2. Theoretical Contributions

The significant contribution of this study was the function of brand attachment and attitude toward the influencer in modulating the influence of social media influencer interactivity and social media influencer authenticity on the impulsive buying behaviour of consumers of Pakistan. It gets the attention of the influencers and their impact on changing consumers' buying behaviour. Social media influencer interactivity and authenticity contribute to knowing the work of influencers on social media, which create a relationship between their follower and them.

7.3. Future Research and Limitations

Because the majority of the sample was made up of young people, the results cannot be extrapolated to the wider public. The study's significance would be bolstered if it were extended to encompass a wider variety of ages, despite the fact that younger generations were more likely to follow social media influencers than prior generations. The impact of proximity on attitudes, word-of-mouth and purchase intention might be examined in other contexts and social media platforms in future research. Influencers and brand managers may want to take a closer look as their profiles grow and change, depending on the data.

References

- Ainin, S., Parveen, F., Moghavvemi, S., Jaafar, N. I., & Shuib, N. L. M. (2015). Factors influencing the use of social media by SMEs and its performance outcomes. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*.
- Audrezet, A., de Kerviler, G., & Moulard, J. G. (2020). Authenticity under threat: When social media influencers need to go beyond self-presentation. *Journal of Business research*, 117, 557-569.
- Aw, E. C.-X., & Labrecque, L. I. (2020). Celebrity endorsement in social media contexts: understanding the role of parasocial interactions and the need to belong. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*.
- Bianchi, C., Andrews, L., Wiese, M., & Fazal-E-Hasan, S. (2017). Consumer intentions to engage in s-commerce: a cross-national study. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 33(5-6), 464-494.
- Britt, R. K., Hayes, J. L., Britt, B. C., & Park, H. (2020). Too big to sell? A computational analysis of network and content characteristics among mega and micro beauty and fashion social media influencers. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 20(2), 111-118.
- Bruhn, M., Schoenmueller, V., & Schäfer, D. B. (2012). Are social media replacing traditional media in terms of brand equity creation? *Management research review*.
- Bukar, U. A., Jabar, M. A., & Sidi, F. (2021). Revisiting Social Media Crisis Communication Model for Building Resilience via Artificial Neural Network Analysis.

- Chen, Y., Lu, Y., Wang, B., & Pan, Z. (2019). How do product recommendations affect impulse buying? An empirical study on WeChat social commerce. *Information & Management*, 56(2), 236-248.
- Chopra, A., Avhad, V., Jaju, & Sonali. (2021). Influencer marketing: An exploratory study to identify antecedents of consumer behaviour of millennial. *Business Perspectives and Research*, 9(1), 77-91.
- Coyle, J. R., Smith, T., & Platt, G. (2012). "I'm here to help": How companies' microblog responses to consumer problems influence brand perceptions. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*.
- De Veirman, M., Cauberghe, V., & Hudders, L. (2017). Marketing through Instagram influencers: the impact of number of followers and product divergence on brand attitude. *International journal of advertising*, 36(5), 798-828.
- Dwivedi, A., & McDonald, R. (2018). Building brand authenticity in fast-moving consumer goods via consumer perceptions of brand marketing communications. *European Journal of marketing*.
- Freberg, K., Graham, K., McGaughey, K., & Freberg, L. A. (2011). Who are the social media influencers? A study of public perceptions of personality. *Public relations review*, 37(1), 90-92.
- Furedi, F. (2010). Introduction to the marketisation of higher education and the student as consumer. In *The marketisation of higher education and the student as consumer* (pp. 15-22). Routledge.
- Howell, E. (2017). Pokémon GO: Implications for literacy in the classroom. *The Reading Teacher*, 70(6), 729-732.
- Kelly, L., Kerr, G., & Drennan, J. (2010). Avoidance of advertising in social networking sites: The teenage perspective. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 10(2), 16-27.
- Ki, C. W. C., & Kim, Y. K. (2019). The mechanism by which social media influencers persuade consumers: The role of consumers' desire to mimic. *Psychology & Marketing*, 36(10), 905-922.
- Kim, J., & Lee, K. H. (2019). Influence of integration on interactivity in social media luxury brand communities. *Journal of Business research*, 99, 422-429.
- Kowalczyk, C. M., & Pounders, K. R. (2016). Transforming celebrities through social media: the role of authenticity and emotional attachment. *Journal of product & brand management*.
- Kusumasondjaja, S. (2019). Exploring the role of visual aesthetics and presentation modality in luxury fashion brand communication on Instagram. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*.
- Lee, S., & Kim, E. (2020). Influencer marketing on Instagram: How sponsorship disclosure, influencer credibility, and brand credibility impact the effectiveness of Instagram promotional post. *Journal of Global Fashion Marketing*, 11(3), 232-249.
- Liu, L., Liu, R., Lee, M., & Chen, J. (2019). When will consumers be ready? A psychological perspective on consumer engagement in social media brand communities. *Internet Research*.
- Lou, C., & Yuan, S. (2019). Influencer marketing: how message value and credibility affect consumer trust of branded content on social media. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 19(1), 58-73.
- Maraz, A., Griffiths, M. D., & Demetrovics, Z. (2016). The prevalence of compulsive buying: a meta-analysis. *Addiction*, 111(3), 408-419.
- Marwick, A. E., & Boyd, D. (2011). I tweet honestly, I tweet passionately: Twitter users, context collapse, and the imagined audience. *New media & society*, 13(1), 114-133.
- Morhart, F., Malär, L., Guèvremont, A., Girardin, F., & Grohmann, B. (2015). Brand authenticity: An integrative framework and measurement scale. *Journal of consumer psychology*, 25(2), 200-218.
- Moulard, J. G., Raggio, R. D., & Folse, J. A. G. (2016). Brand authenticity: Testing the antecedents and outcomes of brand management's passion for its products. *Psychology & Marketing*, 33(6), 421-436.
- Napoli, J., Dickinson-Delaporte, S., & Beverland, M. B. (2016). The brand authenticity continuum: strategic approaches for building value. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 32(13-14), 1201-1229.
- Park, H., & Armstrong, C. M. J. (2019). Is money the biggest driver? Uncovering motives for engaging in online collaborative consumption retail models for apparel. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 51, 42-50.
- Quelhas-Brito, P., Brandão, A., Gadekar, M., & Castelo-Branco, S. (2020). Diffusing fashion information by social media fashion influencers: understanding antecedents and consequences. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*.
- Reinikainen, H., Munnukka, J., Maity, D., & Luoma-aho, V. (2020). 'You really are a great big sister'—parasocial relationships, credibility, and the moderating role of audience comments in influencer marketing. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 36(3-4), 279-298.
- Saad, M., & Metawie, M. (2015). Store environment, personality factors and impulse buying behaviour in Egypt: The mediating roles of shop enjoyment and impulse buying tendencies. *Journal of Business and Management Sciences*, 3(2), 69-77.
- Schallehn, M., Burmann, C., & Riley, N. (2014). Brand authenticity: model development and empirical testing. *Journal of product & brand management*.

- Tatar, Ş. B., & Eren-Erdoğan, İ. (2016). The effect of social media marketing on brand trust and brand loyalty for hotels. *Information Technology & Tourism, 16*(3), 249-263.
- Vukadin, A., Lemoine, J.-F., & Badot, O. (2019). Store artification and retail performance. *Journal of Marketing Management, 35*(7-8), 634-661.
- Weismueller, J., Harrigan, P., Wang, S., & Soutar, G. N. (2020). Influencer endorsements: How advertising disclosure and source credibility affect consumer purchase intention on social media. *Australasian Marketing Journal, 28*(4), 160-170.
- Wu, L., & Stilwell, M. A. (2017). Exploring the marketing potential of location-based mobile games. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing.*
- Xu, X., & Pratt, S. (2018). Social media influencers as endorsers to promote travel destinations: an application of self-congruence theory to the Chinese Generation Y. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing, 35*(7), 958-972.
- Yiu, C. Y., & Xu, S. Y. (2012). A tenant-mix model for shopping malls. *European Journal of marketing.*
- Yu, C., & Bastin, M. (2017). Hedonic shopping value and impulse buying behaviour in transitional economies: A symbiosis in the Mainland China marketplace. In *Advances in Chinese Brand Management* (pp. 316-330). Springer.
- Yu, S., & Hu, Y. (2020). When luxury brands meet China: The effect of localized celebrity endorsements in social media marketing. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services, 54*, 102010.
- Zhang, K. Z., Xu, H., Zhao, S., & Yu, Y. (2018). Online reviews and impulse buying behaviour: the role of browsing and impulsiveness. *Internet Research.*
- Zhang, L., Shao, Z., Li, X., & Feng, Y. (2021). Gamification and online impulse buying: The moderating effect of gender and age. *International Journal of Information Management, 61*, 102267.